

The Chemistry of D : A-Friedooleananes from *Putranjivi roxburghii*

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SINCE the last major reviews^{1,2} on pentacyclic triterpenoids came out, a good number of new D:A-friedooleananes have been isolated from plant sources and their structures determined. The introduction of modern tools like nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy and mass spectrometry have made the task of structure determination much easier. The present review is restricted only to the friedelanes isolated from the different parts of *Putranjiva roxburghii*³, a common Indian plant of the Euphorbiaceae family, which has so far yielded as many as seven triterpenoids that are listed in Table I. Of these only two i.e. friedelin (Ia) and friedelanol (Ib) were known before with their chemistry reviewed⁴. All the remaining five compounds are also derivatives of D:A-friedooleanane, although putranjic acid (IIIa) and putranjivic acid (IVa) are derivatives of 3,4-seco-D:A-friedooleanane.

Putranjivadione⁵

Putranjivadione (IIa)⁵, C₃₀H₄₈O₂ isolated from the trunk bark^{5,6} and root bark⁷ of *P. roxburghii* has two ketonic carbonyl groups, one of them being hindered. The basic skeleton of the diketone was established by its Huang-Minlon reduction to the monoketone (IIc) and finally to friedelane (Id) by the forced Wolff-Kishner reduction of IIc. On reduction with LiAlH₄ putranjivadione (IIa) furnished putranjivadiol (Va) but with NaBH₄ the monohydroxyketone (IIId) was obtained. On forced Wolff-Kishner reduction the latter yielded friedelanol (Ib), thus establishing that one of the carbonyl groups is present at C-3 in IIa. The monoketone (IIc) showed in the NMR spectra in CDCl₃ an AB pattern (2H) centered at 2.20 ppm due to the two protons at C-6 and the C-8 proton appeared as a singlet (1H) at 2.75 ppm. In benzene solution the one proton singlet appeared

TABLE I

Name	Mol. Formula	m.p.	[α] _D
Friedelin (Ia) ^{4,5}	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O	257—261°	—22.4°
Friedelanol (Ib) ^{4,5}	C ₃₀ H ₅₂ O	299—300°	—
Putranjivadione (IIa) ^{5,6}	C ₃₀ H ₄₈ O ₂	284—289°	—36.8°
Roxburgholone (IIb) ^{6,7,10}	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O ₂	312—318°	—7.8°
Putranjic acid (IIIa) ^{6,7,11,12,14}	C ₃₀ H ₅₂ O ₃	218—220°	+ 1°
Putranjivic acid (IVa) ^{13,14}	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O ₂	177—179°	—15°
Roxburghonic acid (Ic) ¹⁵	C ₃₀ H ₄₈ O ₃	340°	—

I

II

- I (a) $R^2 >=O, R^3=H$
 (b) $R^1=R^3=H, R^2=OH$
 (c) $R^2 >=O, R^3=COOH$
 (d) $R^1=R^2=R^3=H$
 (e) $R^2 >=O, R^3=COOMe$
- II (a) $R^2 >=O$
 (b) $R^1=H, R^2=OH$
 (c) $R^1=R^2=H$
 (d) $R^1=OH, R^2=H$

at 2.63 ppm and the AB pattern separated into a pair of doublets at 2.26 and 1.84 ppm. Such a situation can arise only with a carbonyl group at C-7 and at no other position.

The monoketone (IIc) on reduction with $LiAlH_4$ gave the alcohol (VIa) where the axial nature of the

sodium and amyl alcohol, the monoketone could be reduced to the alcohol (VIb) where the hydroxyl group was equatorial and hence much less hindered

Final confirmation of the structure of putranjivadione (IIa) came from mass spectrometric fragmentation pattern, since the mass spectra of D:A-

III

IV

- III (a) $R^1=R^2=H$
 (b) $R^1=Me, R^2=H$
 (c) $R^1=Me, R^2=Ts$
 (d) $R^1=Me, R^2=CS.SMe$
- IV (a) $R=H$
 (b) $R=Me$

hydroxyl was determined from NMR spectra. Due to severe 1, 3-diaxial interactions with the methyl groups at C-5, C-9 and C-14, the hydroxyl group could not be acetylated but could be smoothly dehydrated with catalytic amount of perchloric acid to the olefin (VIIa). On the other hand on reduction with

friedooleananes were well documented^{8,9}. The mass spectrum of putranjivadione (IIa) and the monoketone (IIc) contains a prominent peak at m/e 205 attributed to the ion (VIII) derived from rings D and E. The formation of this ion affords additional evidence for the absence of oxygen function in these rings

V

VI

- V (a) $R^1=OH, R^2=H$
 (b) $R^1=H, R^2=OH$
- VI (a) $R^1=OH, R^2=H$
 (b) $R^1=H, R^2=OH$
- VII (a) $R^1=R^2=H$
 (b) $R^1=H, R^2=OAC$
 (c) $R^1=OAC, R^2=H$
 (d) $R^2 >=O$

VII

in putranjivadione. A peak at m/e 316 in the spectra of putranjivadione (IIa) shifted to m/e 302 in the spectra of friedelin (Ia) and the monoketone (IIc) and corresponded to the ion (IX). A peak at m/e 301 in the spectrum of putranjivadione is located at m/e 287 in friedelin (Ia) and the monoketone (IIc) and evidently this corresponded to the ion (X). Another peak of diagnostic interest in the mass spectrum of putranjivadione (IIa) occurs at m/e 288 corresponding to the ion (XI). This peak is shifted to m/e 274 in the spectra of friedelin (Ia) and the monoketone (IIc). An ion of mass 207 from putranjivadione (IIa) corresponding to one of mass 193 in the monoketone (IIc) was assigned the structure (XII).

Roxburgholone¹⁰

With the structure of putranjivadione (IIa) established the elucidation of the structure¹⁰ of roxburgholone (IIb), $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$ became simple. This compound

with the monohydroxyketone (IIc) obtained from $NaBH_4$ reduction of putranjivadione, since these two hydroxyketones were epimeric at C-3. On reduction with $LiAlH_4$ roxburgholone gave a diol (Vb) which was different from the diol (Va) obtained from putranjivadione on similar treatment. On treatment with acetic anhydride and perchloric the diol (Vb) gave the ene-acetate (VIIb), while the diol (Va) under similar treatment furnished the epimeric ene-acetate (VIIc). Both the ene-acetates were converted to friedel-7-en-3-one (VIIId). These transformations establish beyond doubt that roxburgholone is 3 α -hydroxyfriedelan-7-one (IIb).

Putranjic acid^{11,12,14} and Putranjivic acid^{13,14}

Putranjic acid (IIIa), $C_{30}H_{52}O_3$ isolated from the stem bark^{6,12} and root bark⁷ of *P. roxburghii* readily formed a methyl ester. The third oxygen atom was shown to be present as a secondary hydroxyl group.

isolated from the stem bark^{6,10} and the root bark⁷ of *P. roxburghii* had a hydroxyl group and a ketonic function and on oxidation it furnished putranjivadione (IIa). However roxburgholone was not identical

The NMR spectra of putranjic acid and its methyl ester demonstrated the presence of eight methyl groups intact. It further showed the absence of a CH_2 group α to the carboxylic function. That the

hydroxyl group was situated on the α carbon atom was demonstrated¹¹ by the use of trichloroacetyl isocyanate in NMR studies. This conclusion was further supported¹² by the reduction of methyl putranjate (IIIb) with LiAlH_4 to the vicinal diol (XIII), which on periodate oxidation yielded formaldehyde and the nor-aldehyde (XIV).

Final suggestion for the 3,4-secofriedelane structure of putranjic acid (IIIa) came from mass spectrometric studies^{11,12} of the acid and its derivatives. The peak at m/e 205 corresponded to the ion (VIII) demonstrating the absence of oxygen function in D and E rings. The other ions corresponded well with those from putranjivadiene mentioned earlier and other friedelane derivatives rendering strong support for the suggested structure. The peaks at m/e 218 and 273 were attributed to the ions (XV) and (XVI) respectively showing that there was no oxygen functions in rings B and C also.

The closely related acid, putranjivic acid (IVa), $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_2$ isolated¹³ from the leaves of *P. roxburghii* had also an unhindered carboxyl group. In the NMR spectra its methyl ester (IVb) showed a two proton multiplet corresponding to a CH_2 group α to the carbomethoxy group. The spectra also revealed the presence of a $-\overset{|}{\text{C}}\text{H}=\text{CH}_2$ group, that on ozonolysis gave formaldehyde. The methyl ester in the mass spectra showed peaks corresponding to the ions (VIII), (XV) and (XVI). Finally the tosyl derivative (IIIc) of methyl putranjate on treatment with LiAlH_4 furnished an alcohol identical with the

LiAlH_4 reduction product from methyl dihydro putranjivate, establishing the relationship between the two acids.

Although the above studies left little doubt regarding the correctness of the structures of putranjic acid and putranjivic acids, still the absolute stereochemistry of the molecules remained to be settled. This was done¹⁴ first by converting friedel-3-ene to methyl putranjivate (IVb) thus settling the absolute stereochemistry in putranjivic acid (IVa) in all asymmetric centres and then by fixing the absolute configuration at C-2 in putranjic acid (IIIa).

D:A-friedoolean-3 α , 4 α -diol (XVII) prepared from friedel-3-ene was cleaved with lead tetraacetate to the ketoaldehyde (XVIIIa), which was converted to the ketoester (XVIIIb). The latter was reduced with NaBH_4 to the hydroxyester (XIXa), whose methyl xanthate ester (XIXb) on pyrolysis furnished methyl putranjivate (IVb). Thus the relationship of putranjivic acid (IVa) with D:A-friedooleananes was established¹⁴.

The above transformation settled the structure and stereochemistry of putranjic acid (IIIa) also except the absolute configuration at C-2. The circular dichroism curve of the xanthate ester (IIIId) was utilised for this assignment. Thus IIIId showed a positive Cotton effect around 360 $m\mu$ demonstrating that C-2 has S-configuration in putranjic acid as shown in structure IIIa.

Roxburghonic acid¹⁵

Roxburghonic acid (Ic), C₃₀H₄₈O₃ isolated¹⁵ from the leaves of *P. roxburghii* has a ketonic carbonyl group and a highly hindered carboxylic acid group. In the NMR spectra the methyl ester (Ie) showed the presence of six tertiary and one secondary methyl groups. The ketonic group in Ie could be reduced but the carbomethoxy group was inert towards LiAlH₄. On the basis of mass spectrometric fragmentation pattern of (Ie) the structure of roxburghonic acid has been suggested as (Ic). The peak at m/e 205 corresponding to the ion (VIII) demonstrated that the carbomethoxy group could not be present at C-26, C-27, C-28, C-29 or C-30. The peak at m/e 153 was assigned to the ion (XX) ruling out the possibility of the carbomethoxy group being at C-24. Position C-23 was ruled out on the basis of NMR and the nonreactivity of the ester group. Hence the carbomethoxy group was placed at C-25. This conclusion was supported by the presence of a peak

in the mass spectra at m/e 259 corresponding to the ion (XXI).

The direct correlation of roxburghonic acid (Ic) with D:A-friedooleanes has not been achieved yet.

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